

Low-Temperature Plasma-Enhanced Atomic Layer Deposition of Ga₂O₃ Films Using N₂O

Plasma for Silicon Surface Passivation

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the deposition of gallium oxide (Ga₂O₃) thin films by plasma-enhanced atomic layer deposition (PE-ALD) using nitrous oxide (N₂O) as the oxidant for surface passivation of crystalline silicon. The deposition was performed at a low temperature of 75 °C in a direct-plasma configuration, enabling conformal coating of substrates. Cross-sectional TEM confirmed the amorphous nature of the Ga₂O₃ films and the formation of a thin interfacial SiO_x layer at the substrate interface. STEM-EDX elemental mapping showed a homogeneous distribution of

gallium and oxygen, along with traces of nitrogen and carbon, attributed to precursor–plasma interactions. Optical measurements revealed an optical bandgap of 4.52 eV, consistent with literature values for amorphous Ga₂O₃. It was found that the growth per cycle increased from 0.41 to 0.84 Å/cycle with increasing plasma power; however, higher power and extended plasma exposure deteriorated the passivation quality due to plasma-induced damage at the Ga₂O₃/Si interface. The maximum effective minority carrier lifetime reached 443 μs at a plasma power of 10 W (22 mW/cm²), indicating highly efficient passivation under low-damage deposition conditions. These results demonstrate the potential of N₂O-based PE-ALD Ga₂O₃ films as wide-bandgap, low-temperature passivation layers for next-generation silicon solar cells.

KEYWORDS

Gallium oxide; Plasma-enhanced atomic layer deposition; N₂O plasma; Surface passivation; Optical bandgap; Silicon solar cells.

1. INTRODUCTION

Surface passivation of crystalline silicon remains one of the key challenges in the development of high-efficiency silicon-based photovoltaic devices. Effective suppression of carrier recombination at the surface requires the formation of thin, chemically stable films with a minimal density of interface states [1,2]. Transition metal oxides such as V₂O_x, MoO_x, and TiO_x have demonstrated excellent selectivity in charge carrier transport, making them promising candidates for integration into high-efficiency silicon solar cells [3–6]. However, these oxides do not provide direct surface passivation and are typically used in combination with additional passivating layers, such as hydrogenated amorphous silicon (a-Si:H).

Gallium oxide (Ga_2O_3), a wide-bandgap semiconductor with a bandgap of 4.5–4.8 eV [7], is considered a promising material for both surface passivation and selective contact formation in silicon solar cells. It has already found applications in power electronics [8] and solar-blind ultraviolet photodetectors [9,10]. Previous studies have shown that Ga_2O_3 can significantly suppress surface recombination on silicon, primarily due to its high negative fixed charge and low defect density after low-temperature annealing, enabling the fabrication of high-efficiency silicon solar cells [11–14].

Atomic layer deposition (ALD) provides atomic-level control over film thickness and composition, allowing for the formation of highly uniform ultrathin passivating layers. In particular, plasma-enhanced atomic layer deposition (PE-ALD), which utilizes plasma to activate oxidation reactions, offers greater control over the density, composition, and structural properties of the resulting oxide films [15]. Ga_2O_3 films deposited by PE-ALD have been reported to deliver more effective surface passivation of silicon compared to thermally grown Ga_2O_3 , with correspondingly higher minority carrier lifetimes [16]. Moreover, the use of O_2 plasma in PE-ALD has been shown to enable the deposition of uniform amorphous Ga_2O_3 films with controlled thickness at low temperatures [17]. Ga_2O_3 films prepared by PE-ALD exhibit high optical transparency and can be doped with silicon, enabling the development of selective contacts with low contact resistance [18,19]. Thus, low-temperature PE-ALD of gallium oxide emerges as a promising approach for surface passivation in advanced silicon solar cell architectures.

Typically, plasma-activated oxidants such as O_2 plasma or ozone (O_3) are used as oxygen sources during PE-ALD of Ga_2O_3 . However, recent studies have shown that nitrous oxide (N_2O) can serve as an alternative oxidant, improving the quality of oxide films and reducing defect density in the PE-ALD of materials such as SiO_2 and HfO_2 [20,21]. N_2O has also been successfully

used in the PE-ALD of Al₂O₃, where it produced films with excellent electrical and structural characteristics [22]. In particular, N₂O plasma was found to promote the formation of dense, uniform Al₂O₃ films with a low defect density [23]. These advantages make N₂O a promising oxidant for the deposition of oxide layers in a variety of microelectronic and photonic applications.

In this work, we investigate the use of N₂O plasma in the PE-ALD of Ga₂O₃ for surface passivation of crystalline silicon. The growth per cycle (GPC) rate was determined from thickness measurements using ellipsometry. The structural properties and composition of the Ga₂O₃ layers were examined using transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX). Optical absorption measurements were also performed to evaluate the optical properties of the films and to determine their band gap width. Additionally, we present results on the passivation quality as a function of the deposition conditions. In contrast to conventional PE-ALD processes employing O₂ or O₃ as oxidants, this study utilizes direct N₂O plasma, which provides a soft oxidation environment and allows low-temperature deposition. The influence of N₂O plasma parameters on the passivation efficiency of Si by Ga₂O₃ films is systematically analyzed for the first time.

2. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The experiments were conducted on p-type silicon wafers with a thickness of 380 μm. The substrates were fabricated by the float-zone method and featured double-side polished surfaces. Their specific resistivity 1-5 Ω·cm, making them well-suited for evaluating surface passivation quality. Under conditions of double-side passivation, the effective minority carrier lifetime (τ_{eff}) approaches the bulk value and can be described by the following expression:

$$\tau_{\text{eff}}^{-1} = \tau_{\text{bulk}}^{-1} + 2S/W$$

where τ_{bulk} is the bulk minority carrier lifetime, S is the surface recombination velocity, and W is the wafer thickness. The maximum τ_{eff} in the as-received wafers reaches approximately 3 ms, as confirmed by symmetrical double-sided passivation using optimized a-Si:H layers. With high-quality passivation, the measured τ_{eff} reflects the actual bulk lifetime of the silicon. This value was used as a reference for evaluating the passivation quality of the Ga_2O_3 layers. The Ga_2O_3 films were deposited on the silicon substrates using a PE-ALD process in an Oxford Instruments Plasmalab 100 PECVD system equipped with a 13.56 MHz direct plasma source. The ALD chamber features parallel-plate electrodes, with the gas showerhead and the heated substrate table simultaneously serving as RF electrodes. The PE-ALD process relies on self-limiting surface reactions between precursor molecules introduced in alternating pulses, with intermediate purge steps to prevent gas-phase reactions. This ensures sequential, layer-by-layer deposition based solely on surface chemistry (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of Ga_2O_3 step-by-step film formation by PE-ALD using N_2O plasma.

Trimethylgallium (TMG, $\text{Ga}(\text{CH}_3)_3$) and nitrous oxide (N_2O) were used as gallium and oxygen precursors, respectively. TMG was delivered through a bubbler purged with high-purity hydrogen,

resulting in a concentration of 2% in the TMG/H₂ gas mixture. The deposition temperature was maintained at 75 °C using the heated substrate table. Low temperature was chosen to increase hydrogen content in the film, which is known to enhance the passivation quality of the silicon surface [16]. Prior to deposition, silicon substrates were cleaned in a 10% HF/H₂O solution to remove the native oxide. During the oxidation step, N₂O was activated using a capacitively coupled RF plasma with power ranging from 10 W to 200 W, corresponding to a power density of 22–440 mW/cm². The parameters of each PE-ALD cycle are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. PE-ALD cycle parameters for Ga₂O₃ deposition with N₂O plasma.

Step	Duration, s	Gas composition	Flow rate, sccm	Pressure, mTorr	Power, W
TMG exposure	5	TMG/H ₂	100/10 0	350	0
Purge	10	Ar	100	0	0
Pressure stabilization	4	N ₂ O	200	350	0
N₂O plasma	5-15	N ₂ O	200	350	10-200
Purge	12	Ar	100	0	0

The thickness of the deposited Ga₂O₃ films was measured using fixed-angle laser ellipsometry at a wavelength of 632 nm. Assuming a smooth, transparent layer on a silicon substrate, the resulting film thickness was extracted based on the single-layer optical model. The optical properties of the Ga₂O₃ films deposited by PE-ALD were analyzed using a spectroscopic setup equipped with a silicon-based CCD spectrometer (Avantes Avaspec 2048XL), covering the spectral range of 200–1200 nm. For these measurements, Ga₂O₃ was deposited onto a double-side

polished fused silica substrate (thickness: 400 μm). Transmission and reflection spectra were recorded for both coated and uncoated substrates to assess the optical response of the Ga_2O_3 layer.

The morphology of the resulting structures was examined using a SUPRA 25 Zeiss scanning electron microscope (SEM) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM). Structural analysis was carried out on a JEOL JEM-2100F microscope operating at 200 kV, using both TEM imaging and electron diffraction. Elemental composition was analyzed in the TEM setup using energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), to assess the uniformity of the Ga_2O_3 film composition. Cross-sectional samples were prepared for EDX analysis under the same geometry as TEM. Measurements were conducted in two modes: point composition analysis and elemental mapping across the film-substrate interface.

To evaluate the τ_{eff} in the silicon substrates, symmetric test structures were fabricated by depositing Ga_2O_3 layers on both sides of the wafer. After the first side was coated, the wafer was removed from the chamber, flipped, and reloaded for the second-side deposition. Notably, no additional HF treatment was applied before the second deposition to avoid damage to the thin Ga_2O_3 film, which is highly sensitive to hydrofluoric acid. As a result, symmetric $\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Si}/\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3$ test structures were obtained using p-type wafers. Rapid thermal annealing (RTA) at 250 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 20 minutes in a high-purity (99.999%) nitrogen atmosphere was performed to improve surface passivation. Low annealing temperatures and extended annealing times are known to enhance passivation quality [11]. Annealing reduces defect density at the interface and increases fixed charge in the Ga_2O_3 layer, leading to field-effect passivation. As a result, the $\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Si}$ interface has less influence on electron-hole recombination, and the effective lifetime is significantly increased. The τ_{eff} was measured by photoluminescence decay method using an infrared laser source at 850 nm. A detailed description of the measurement setup is provided elsewhere [24].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To determine the growth rate of Ga₂O₃ films deposited by PE-ALD, a series of processes with varying numbers of deposition cycles was carried out. Ga₂O₃ layers were deposited on planar p-type silicon substrates under identical conditions, with the number of ALD cycles set to 100, 200, and 800. The direct RF plasma power during the N₂O step was fixed at 20 W (44 mW/cm²), and the plasma exposure time was 5 seconds. The resulting film thicknesses and calculated average growth-per-cycle values are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Thickness of Ga₂O₃ films grown on silicon substrates by PE-ALD as a function of the number of ALD cycles (N₂O plasma power: 20 W).

The Ga₂O₃ film thickness exhibits a linear dependence on the number of ALD cycles, confirming the self-limiting nature of the surface reactions that are characteristic of atomic layer deposition. Minor deviations from ideal linearity are attributed to the uncertainty in ellipsometric measurements, particularly for ultrathin films. The average growth rate of 0.49 Å/cycle at 20 W N₂O plasma power is significantly lower than the theoretical monolayer thickness (~3 Å/cycle) for amorphous Ga₂O₃. This reduced growth rate can be attributed to the steric hindrance effect inherent to metalorganic precursors used in ALD processes [25]. Due to the finite size of TMG molecules, uniform surface coverage within a single cycle is not achievable, resulting in partial

chemisorption with intermolecular gaps. Consequently, surface reactions occur non-uniformly, leading to a lower effective growth rate per cycle [26]. Nevertheless, the measured growth rate is consistent with literature reports on PE-ALD of Ga_2O_3 , where values typically range from 0.5 to 1.5 Å/cycle depending on the different precursors and deposition conditions [17,27]. The structural properties of Ga_2O_3 films were investigated using transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and selected area electron diffraction (SAED). For this purpose, Ga_2O_3 was deposited on crystalline silicon (100) substrates using 800 PE-ALD cycles at a plasma power of 200 W (440 mW/cm²). A cross-sectional scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of the Ga_2O_3 layer taken at a tilt angle of 20° is shown in Figure 3a.

Figure 3. (a) Tilted (20°) cross-section SEM image of the cleaved Ga₂O₃/Si structure; (b) SAED pattern of the Ga₂O₃ layer confirming amorphous structure; (c) Cross-section TEM image of the Ga₂O₃ layer on silicon; (d) High-magnification TEM image of the selected interface area.

The SEM analysis of the cleaved cross-section and surface reveals a smooth Ga₂O₃ layer with no visible inclusions or crystallite segregation. Such morphology is typical of amorphous Ga₂O₃ films. The tilted SEM image of the frontal surface further confirms the absence of structural defects, indicating uniform and conformal deposition over a large area. Figure 3c,d shows a cross-sectional TEM image of the Ga₂O₃ layer along with the corresponding SAED pattern (Figure 3b).

According to the bright-field TEM micrograph, the Ga₂O₃ film appears as a uniform planar layer with low surface roughness. No interfacial or bulk defects were observed in either the Ga₂O₃ layer or the near-surface region of the silicon substrate. A thin (~2–3 nm) interfacial silicon oxide (SiO_x) layer, appearing with brighter contrast, was observed at the Ga₂O₃/Si interface. The reduced contrast is attributed to the lower atomic numbers of Si and O compared to Ga, resulting in weaker electron scattering in bright-field mode. This SiO_x layer is formed during the initial stages of deposition due to the interaction of the silicon surface with reactive species from the N₂O plasma. The thickness of the Ga₂O₃ film deposited in 800 cycles at 200 W plasma power was measured to be approximately 60 nm, which is consistent with ellipsometric measurements. The SAED pattern of the Ga₂O₃ film on silicon exhibits distinct diffraction spots from the crystalline silicon substrate and a diffuse halo ring, indicating the absence of long-range atomic order. Therefore, the Ga₂O₃ film deposited by PE-ALD at 75 °C is fully amorphous. Local elemental analysis of the Ga₂O₃ films deposited on silicon substrates was performed using scanning transmission electron microscopy with energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (STEM-EDX), including elemental mapping across the cross-section of the samples. Both point EDX spectra and elemental distribution maps were acquired for the Ga₂O₃/Si interface region (Figure 4a).

Figure 4. (a) EDX spectrum of the Ga_2O_3 layer on a silicon substrate; (b) STEM image of the cross-section of the $\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Si}$ structure; (c) STEM-EDX elemental maps of Si, Ga, O, N, and C across the Ga_2O_3 layer and interface region.

STEM-EDX analysis confirmed the presence of the main elements constituting Ga_2O_3 — gallium and oxygen — within the film. A strong silicon signal was also detected due to the underlying substrate. Additional peaks from copper and carbon were observed, originating from the Cu TEM grid and the epoxy resin used during sample preparation, respectively. A weak but reproducible nitrogen signal was detected, which may indicate partial incorporation of nitrogen into the Ga_2O_3 matrix during plasma-assisted deposition using N_2O . The STEM image of the analyzed region (Figure 4b) clearly shows the boundary between the silicon substrate and the Ga_2O_3 film, enabling accurate correlation with elemental maps. According to the EDX mapping (Figure 4c), the silicon signal dominates within the substrate, while gallium and oxygen are uniformly distributed within the film, corresponding to the expected composition of gallium oxide. Nitrogen distribution maps reveal a weak but consistent signal within the Ga_2O_3 layer, suggesting that nitrogen incorporation results from the interaction of N_2O plasma species with the growing oxide film, rather than from contamination. A very weak nitrogen signal is detected in the substrate region, but its intensity is close to the noise level and does not indicate any measurable nitrogen incorporation into Si substrate.

The carbon map shows high intensity in the epoxy resin regions outside the Ga_2O_3 layer, consistent with sample encapsulation. However, a weak carbon signal was also observed within the Ga_2O_3 layer itself, likely due to partial incorporation of carbon resulting from plasma-induced decomposition of CH_3 - ligands from the TMG precursor. Overall, the STEM-EDX results confirm the high chemical uniformity of the Ga_2O_3 layers deposited by PE-ALD using N_2O plasma. The

minor incorporation of nitrogen and carbon into the film is attributed to the specific plasma conditions and precursor chemistry and does not lead to detectable phase separation or structural inhomogeneity. These findings validate the deposition conditions used in this work as suitable for forming chemically stable, high-quality layers of Ga_2O_3 . For use in advanced silicon-based photovoltaic devices, Ga_2O_3 deposited by PE-ALD must exhibit favorable optical properties—specifically, low absorption in the operating spectral range of silicon solar cells (300–1200 nm or 1–4 eV). To investigate these characteristics, a Ga_2O_3 film was deposited on a double-side polished fused silica substrate using 800 PE-ALD cycles with an N_2O plasma power of 200 W, resulting in a thickness of approximately 60 nm. A bare fused silica substrate was used as a reference. Reflection and transmission spectra were measured for both the coated and uncoated substrates. Based on these measurements, the absorption coefficient (α) was calculated in the photon energy ($h\nu$) range of 1.2 to 6 eV (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Absorption spectrum of a 60 nm-thick Ga_2O_3 film deposited on fused silica by PE-ALD.

Inset: Tauc plot $((\alpha h\nu)^{1/2}$ vs. $h\nu$) used to determine the optical bandgap of the indirect semiconductor.

The absorption spectra clearly demonstrate a difference between the reference and Ga₂O₃-coated substrates. The Ga₂O₃ film shows high optical transparency across the infrared, visible, and near-UV ranges, with significant absorption only for $h\nu$ exceeding ~ 4.7 eV. This transparency makes Ga₂O₃ suitable for use as a wide-bandgap front window layer in silicon solar cells. Particularly, Ga₂O₃ is a promising candidate for passivating highly textured silicon surfaces with large aspect ratios, where conventional a-Si:H layers suffer from limited conformality and significant optical absorption [28]. Based on the obtained absorption spectrum, a Tauc plot was constructed in the form of $(\alpha h\nu)^{1/2}$ vs. $h\nu$, corresponding to an indirect optical transition. Linear fitting of the high-energy region followed by extrapolation to the photon energy axis yielded an optical bandgap of 4.52 eV. This value is in a good agreement with previously reported optical bandgaps of amorphous Ga₂O₃ films deposited by PE-ALD, typically ranging from 4.5 to 4.9 eV depending on the choice of precursors and deposition conditions. The combination of optical transparency and good surface passivation performance highlights the potential of amorphous Ga₂O₃ for use in advanced silicon-based photovoltaic devices. In PE-ALD processes employing direct RF plasma sources, it is crucial to evaluate the impact of N₂O plasma exposure on the silicon substrate during Ga₂O₃ film deposition. To this end, the influence of both plasma exposure time and RF power on the surface passivation quality was investigated. To assess the effect of plasma duration, symmetric test structures were fabricated, in which both sides of p-type silicon wafers were coated with Ga₂O₃ films. The number of deposition cycles on each side was fixed at 100, corresponding to a film thickness of approximately 5 nm. During the N₂O step, the RF plasma power was held constant at 20 W, while the plasma exposure time was varied between 5 and 15 seconds. To provide a more detailed analysis of the surface passivation quality, the time-resolved photoluminescence decay curves were measured for all samples after RTA annealing. The

excitation was performed using a pulsed 850 nm laser, and the luminescence decay was recorded using a photodiode. The decay transients were fitted by a single exponential function

$$I(t) = I_0 \cdot \exp(-t/\tau_{\text{eff}})$$

allowing the extraction of the effective carrier lifetime. The time-resolved photoluminescence (PL) decay curves measured after RTA (Figure 6a) show a noticeable reduction in carrier lifetime with increasing N₂O plasma exposure time, indicating degradation of surface passivation. The maximum effective minority carrier lifetime in the wafers, as a function of N₂O step duration, is presented in Figure 6b.

Figure 6. (a) Time-resolved photoluminescence decay curves of silicon substrates passivated with Ga₂O₃ layers deposited by PE-ALD at different N₂O plasma exposure times. (b) Maximum τ_{eff} in silicon wafers passivated with Ga₂O₃ films, measured before and after RTA, as a function of N₂O plasma step time.

Immediately after Ga₂O₃ deposition, the τ_{eff} remained at ~10 μs, similar to the baseline lifetime of the untreated substrates, indicating minimal initial passivation. However, following rapid thermal annealing (RTA) at 250 °C for 20 minutes in high-purity nitrogen, the lifetime increased significantly — reaching up to 293 μs for a N₂O exposure time of 5 s. In contrast, longer N₂O steps

led to reduced τ_{eff} after annealing, decreasing to 72 μs and 34 μs for plasma durations of 10 s and 15 s, respectively. Despite the relatively low RF plasma power (20 W), prolonged exposure negatively affected the surface passivation quality. A similar trend was previously observed in PE-ALD of Ga_2O_3 using ozone (O_3) as an oxidant [16]. The reduction in τ_{eff} is likely attributed to plasma-induced damage at the $\text{Ga}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Si}$ interface and in the near-surface region of the silicon substrate. Even at minimal RF power, ion bombardment and vacuum ultraviolet radiation both intrinsic to plasma discharges may introduce interfacial defects. These results highlight the critical importance of minimizing plasma exposure time to achieve optimal surface passivation of silicon using Ga_2O_3 films deposited by PE-ALD with N_2O plasma. Next, the influence of RF plasma power on both the growth rate of Ga_2O_3 films and the passivation quality of silicon surfaces was investigated. Symmetric test structures were fabricated by depositing Ga_2O_3 films on both sides of p-type silicon substrates using 100 PE-ALD cycles. The duration of the N_2O step was fixed at 5 s, while the RF plasma power during this step was varied from 10 W to 200 W. After deposition, all samples underwent rapid thermal annealing at 250 °C for 20 minutes. The time-resolved photoluminescence (PL) decay curves measured after RTA (Figure 7a) show a noticeable reduction in carrier lifetime with increasing N_2O plasma power, indicating degradation of surface passivation. The resulting film growth rate and τ_{eff} were analyzed as a function of plasma power (Figure 7b).

Figure 7. (a) Time-resolved photoluminescence decay curves of silicon substrates passivated with Ga₂O₃ layers deposited by PE-ALD at different N₂O plasma power. (b) Influence of N₂O plasma power during PE-ALD of Ga₂O₃ on the growth rate and τ_{eff} in p-type silicon. (c) Lifetime mapping across a sample passivated at 10 W N₂O plasma power. Slight non-uniformity at the wafer edges results from plasma intensity variations in the direct RF configuration.

As the plasma power increased from 10 W to 100 W, the growth rate of the Ga₂O₃ film increased by approximately 50%, from 0.41 to 0.84 $\text{\AA}/\text{cycle}$. This enhancement is attributed to the higher density of reactive oxygen species in the plasma, which accelerates surface reactions and improves precursor oxidation. At low plasma powers, the insufficient oxidation of TMG molecules may lead

to sub-stoichiometric Ga₂O₃ films with reduced oxygen content. Once the plasma power reaches 100 W, oxidation becomes sufficient to saturate the surface reactions, and the growth rate becomes limited by the surface coverage of chemisorbed precursor molecules — a characteristic signature of a self-limiting ALD process. Additionally, deposition at elevated plasma powers may lead to the formation of Ga–N bonds, which could also influence the resulting film thickness and composition [29].

While increasing plasma power enhances the growth rate, it negatively affects the passivation quality. A clear degradation in τ_{eff} is observed with increasing plasma power, consistent with prior observations for Ga₂O₃ films grown using ozone-based PE-ALD [30]. This degradation is attributed to plasma-induced damage at the Ga₂O₃/Si interface, particularly at powers exceeding 50 W. At low plasma powers (10–20 W), high carrier lifetimes of 443 μs and 293 μs are achieved, indicating effective passivation and minimal interfacial damage. However, in the range of 20–50 W, τ_{eff} drops by more than an order of magnitude, reaching 13 μs at 50 W, suggesting the presence of a critical plasma power threshold beyond which irreversible damage is introduced due to ion bombardment and chemical attack during the N₂O plasma step [31]. At higher deposition powers (100–200 W), τ_{eff} remain low (13–18 μs), indicating persistent damage to the silicon surface. In this regime, the increase in growth rate does not compensate for the degradation in interface quality, making the passivating layer ineffective.

To provide a more quantitative assessment of the surface passivation quality, the measured τ_{eff} values were converted into the implied open-circuit voltage (iV_{oc}) under one-sun equivalent conditions. The conversion was performed according to the relationship between the excess carrier density (Δn), recombination lifetime, and quasi-Fermi level splitting [32]. The iV_{oc} values for samples deposited at low plasma power (10–20 W) reached 640–660 mV, confirming that Ga₂O₃

films grown under soft N₂O plasma conditions provide strong field-effect and chemical passivation of the Si surface. To evaluate the uniformity of surface passivation, lifetime mapping was performed on a sample passivated at the lowest plasma power (10 W), shown in Figure 7c. The obtained data show that the effective lifetime is highly uniform across the central part of the wafer, while a slight decrease is observed near the edges. This non-uniformity originates from plasma distribution effects in the direct-plasma configuration of the PE-ALD system, where ion density and UV photon flux are higher near the periphery. Nevertheless, the majority of the wafer area exhibits lifetime values above 400 μs, confirming that the process provides overall uniform and reproducible passivation. These results confirm the effectiveness of low-power PE-ALD using N₂O plasma in producing high-quality, uniform passivation layers.

Overall, the findings highlight that maintaining low plasma power in the 10–20 W range is critical to ensure effective passivation of silicon wafers with Ga₂O₃. Although this regime results in a slower growth rate, it is essential for preserving the structural integrity of the interface. The sharp drop in τ_{eff} at plasma powers of 50 W and above provides direct evidence of the dominant role of plasma-induced damage and defines the upper boundary of the technological window for passivation-sensitive applications.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the feasibility of forming passivating Ga₂O₃ layers on silicon surfaces using PE-ALD with N₂O plasma. The optical properties of the Ga₂O₃ films obtained by PE-ALD are consistent with literature values: the optical bandgap was determined to be 4.52 eV, and the high transmittance in the visible and infrared ranges confirms the materials potential as a wide-bandgap front side passivating contact. Structural characterization by SEM and TEM revealed smooth, uniform, amorphous Ga₂O₃ layers with low surface roughness. A thin interfacial SiO_x

layer was observed at the Ga₂O₃/Si interface, likely formed during the initial ALD cycles due to the interaction of the silicon surface with reactive plasma species. STEM-EDX elemental analysis confirmed the film composition, with minor incorporation of carbon and nitrogen attributed to partial decomposition of the TMG precursor and Ga–N bond formation. These impurities were homogeneously distributed and did not disrupt the overall film uniformity. The growth rate was found to vary from 0.41 Å/cycle at low plasma power to 0.84 Å/cycle at 100 W and above. However, increasing both the plasma power and exposure time was shown to negatively affect the passivation quality. In the direct plasma configuration used in this study, even moderate plasma parameters resulted in plasma-induced interface damage, causing a significant reduction in τ_{eff} . The high effective minority carrier lifetime, up to 443 μs ($iV_{\text{oc}}=665$ mV), was achieved under minimal plasma power and short exposure times, indicating the high passivation quality attainable under optimized deposition conditions. Overall, amorphous Ga₂O₃ offers a unique combination of excellent surface coverage, low optical absorption, and effective chemical and field-effect passivation, providing a viable route toward advanced passivating contacts for next-generation photovoltaic technologies.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Ding Z, Kan C, Jiang S, Zhang M, Zhang H, Liu W, et al. Highly passivated TOPCon bottom cells for perovskite/silicon tandem solar cells. *Nat Commun* 2024;15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-52309-2>
- [2] Walter A, Kamino BA, Moon S-J, Wyss P, Diaz Leon JJ, Allebé C, et al. Rear textured p-type high temperature passivating contacts and their implementation in perovskite/silicon tandem cells. *Energy Adv* 2023;2(11):1818–22. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d3ya00048f>
- [3] Li J, Pan T, Wang J, Cao S, Lin Y, Hoex B, et al. Bilayer MoOx/CrOx passivating contact targeting highly stable silicon heterojunction solar cells. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces* 2020;12(32):36778–86. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.0c09877>
- [4] Nasser H, Es F, Zolfaghari Borra M, Semiz E, Kökbudak G, Orhan E, et al. On the application of hole-selective MoOx as full-area rear contact for industrial scale p-type c-Si solar cells. *Prog Photovolt* 2020;29(3):281–93. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pip.3363>
- [5] Shehata MM, Phang P, Basnet R, Yin Y, Kremer F, Bartholazzi G, et al. Outstanding surface passivation for highly efficient silicon solar cells enabled by innovative AlyTiOx/TiOx electron-selective contact stack. *Sol RRL* 2022;6(10). <https://doi.org/10.1002/solr.202200550>
- [6] Masmitjà G, Gerling LG, Ortega P, Puigdollers J, Martín I, Voz C, et al. V2Ox-based hole-selective contacts for c-Si interdigitated back-contacted solar cells. *J Mater Chem A* 2017;5(19):9182–9. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7ta01959a>
- [7] Biswas M, Nishinaka H. Thermodynamically metastable α -, ϵ - (or κ -), and γ -Ga2O3: From material growth to device applications. *APL Mater* 2022;10(6). <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0085360>

- [8] Feng Z, Tian X, Li Z, Hu Z, Zhang Y, Kang X, et al. Normally-off beta-Ga₂O₃ power MOSFET with ferroelectric charge storage gate stack structure. *IEEE Electron Device Lett* 2020;41(3):333–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/led.2020.2970066>
- [9] Zhang L, Xiu X, Li Y, Zhu Y, Hua X, Xie Z, et al. Solar-blind ultraviolet photodetector based on vertically aligned single-crystalline β -Ga₂O₃ nanowire arrays. *Nanophotonics* 2020;9(15):4497–503. <https://doi.org/10.1515/nanoph-2020-0295>
- [10] Bae J, Park J-H, Jeon D-W, Kim J. Self-powered solar-blind α -Ga₂O₃ thin-film UV-C photodiode grown by halide vapor-phase epitaxy. *APL Mater* 2021;9(10). <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0067133>
- [11] Allen TG, Ernst M, Samundsett C, Cuevas A. Demonstration of c-Si solar cells with gallium oxide surface passivation and laser-doped gallium P⁺ regions. In: *Proc IEEE PVSC*. 2015. p. 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/pvsc.2015.7356405>
- [12] Allen TG, Cuevas A. Plasma enhanced atomic layer deposition of gallium oxide on crystalline silicon: Demonstration of surface passivation and negative interfacial charge. *Phys Status Solidi RRL* 2015;9(4):220–4. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssr.201510056>
- [13] Allen TG, Wan YY, Cuevas A. Silicon surface passivation by gallium oxide capped with silicon nitride. *IEEE J Photovolt* 2016;6(4):900–5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/jphotov.2016.2566881>
- [14] Allen TG, Cuevas A. Electronic passivation of silicon surfaces by thin films of atomic layer deposited gallium oxide. *Appl Phys Lett* 2014;105(3). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4890737>
- [15] Profijt HB, Potts SE, van de Sanden MCM, Kessels WMM. Plasma-assisted atomic layer deposition: Basics, opportunities, and challenges. *J Vac Sci Technol A* 2011;29(5). <https://doi.org/10.1116/1.3609974>

- [16] Hiller D, Julin J, Chnani A, Strehle S. Silicon surface passivation by ALD-Ga₂O₃: Thermal vs. plasma-enhanced atomic layer deposition. *IEEE J Photovolt* 2020;10(4):959–68. <https://doi.org/10.1109/jphotov.2020.2989201>
- [17] Yang Y, Zhang X-Y, Wang C, Ren F-B, Zhu R-F, Hsu C-H, et al. Compact Ga₂O₃ thin films deposited by plasma enhanced atomic layer deposition at low temperature. *Nanomaterials* 2022;12(9):1510. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano12091510>
- [18] Zhang X-Y, Yang Y, Fan W-H, Wang C, Wu W-Y, Tseng M-C, et al. Growth and characterization of Si-doped Ga₂O₃ thin films by remote plasma atomic layer deposition: Toward UVC-LED application. *Surf Coat Technol* 2022;435:128252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2022.128252>
- [19] Villora EG, Shimamura K, Yoshikawa Y, Ujiie T, Aoki K. Electrical conductivity and carrier concentration control in β-Ga₂O₃ by Si doping. *Appl Phys Lett* 2008;92(20). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2919728>
- [20] Kim D-G, Yoo KS, Kim H, Park J-S. Impact of N₂O plasma reactant on PEALD-SiO₂ insulator for remarkably reliable ALD-oxide semiconductor TFTs. *SSRN J* 2022. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4037189>
- [21] Kim S, Kim J, Choi J, Kang H, Jeon H, Bae C. Characteristics of HfO₂ thin films deposited by plasma-enhanced atomic layer deposition using O₂ plasma and N₂O plasma. *J Vac Sci Technol B* 2006;24(3):1088–93. <https://doi.org/10.1116/1.2188405>
- [22] Lee S, Jeon H. Characteristics of an Al₂O₃ thin film deposited by a plasma enhanced atomic layer deposition method using N₂O plasma. *Electron Mater Lett* 2007;3(1):17–21. <https://scholarworks.bwise.kr/hanyang/handle/2021.sw.hanyang/180409>

- [23] Kim SJ, Yong SH, Choi YJ, Hwangbo H, Yang W-Y, Chae H. Flexible Al₂O₃/plasma polymer multilayer moisture barrier films deposited by a spatial atomic layer deposition process. *J Vac Sci Technol A* 2020;38(2). <https://doi.org/10.1116/1.5130727>
- [24] Kudryashov D, Gudovskikh A, Uvarov A, Nikitina E. Investigation of silicon wafers thermal degradation by photoluminescence decay measurements. *AIP Conf Proc* 2018;2012:040005. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5053513>
- [25] Tezsevin I, Deijkers JH, Merckx MJM, Kessels WMM, Sandoval TE, Mackus AJM. The consequences of random sequential adsorption for the precursor packing and growth-per-cycle of atomic layer deposition processes. *J Phys Chem Lett* 2024;15(29):7496–501. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcclett.4c01632>
- [26] Richey NE, de Paula C, Bent SF. Understanding chemical and physical mechanisms in atomic layer deposition. *J Chem Phys* 2020;152(4). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5133390>
- [27] O'Donoghue R, Rechmann J, Aghaee M, Rogalla D, Becker H-W, Creatore M, et al. Low temperature growth of gallium oxide thin films via plasma enhanced atomic layer deposition. *Dalton Trans* 2017;46(47):16551–61. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7dt03427j>
- [28] Gudovskikh AS, Baranov AI, Uvarov AV, Vyacheslavova EA, Maksimova AA, Salimi A, et al. Interface properties study of black silicon solar cells with front surface a-Si:H/c-Si heterojunction. *J Phys D Appl Phys* 2024;58(4):045101. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6463/ad8a6d>
- [29] Tang WH, Liu BW, Zhang BC, Li M, Xia Y. Low temperature depositions of GaN thin films by plasma-enhanced atomic layer deposition. *Acta Phys Sin* 2017;66(9):098101. <https://doi.org/10.7498/aps.66.098101>

- [30] Ma D, Liu W, Xiao M, Yang Z, Liu Z, Liao M, et al. Highly improved passivation of PECVD p-type TOPCon by suppressing plasma-oxidation ion-bombardment-induced damages. *Sol Energy* 2022;242:1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2022.07.003>
- [31] Nunomura S, Tsutsumi T, Takada N, Fukasawa M, Hori M. Radical, ion, and photon's effects on defect generation at SiO₂/Si interface during plasma etching. *Appl Surf Sci* 2024;672:160764. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2024.160764>
- [32] Macdonald, D., Cuevas, A., 2000. The use of injection-level dependent lifetime measurements for determining solar cell parameters. *Proc. 38th Annu. Conf. Aust. N.Z. Sol. Energy Soc.*, Brisbane, Australia, pp. 494–500.